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Title: Walking to access shared mobility services: a case study in Palermo, Italy

Authors: Gabriele D'Orso*¹, Marco Migliore²

¹ *Department of Engineering, University of Palermo, Palermo, Italy, gabriele.dorso@unipa.it*

² *Department of Engineering, University of Palermo, Palermo, Italy, marco.migliore@unipa.it*

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Abstract

Walking is the main mode to access shared mobility services like carsharing and bikesharing. Indeed, before starting the in-vehicle trip, carsharing and bikesharing users must reach the pick-up stations in the station-based systems or the locations where the shared vehicles were parked by other users inside the service area in the free-floating services.

Although the ease with which individuals can access shared vehicles appears to be fundamental, few researchers have specifically investigated how to measure station and vehicle accessibility [1]. The study aims to analyze how much the pedestrian accessibility and the walkability of the urban areas around the carsharing stations and bikesharing docks affect the use of these services by citizens. The physical characteristics of the built environment are widely recognized to influence people's willingness to walk and cycle in urban neighborhoods and could affect the access to shared mobility, their use, and the membership rate. Thus, the research used Palermo, Italy, as a case study to assess and compare the contribution of different accessibility indicators to modeling carsharing and bikesharing use, considering some indicators deriving from the literature, like the Pedestrian Catchment Area ratio used by Schlossberg [2]. In Palermo, the municipal public transportation company AMAT manages a dock-based bikesharing service and a carsharing service, called Amigo, which can be used as a station-based service but also as a free-floating service, using in the latter case a fleet of 24 electric vehicles. The 2019 data of the Palermo shared mobility services were analyzed; using this period of time, the behaviors by users were not affected by the Covid-19 pandemic and the launching of several scooter-sharing and dockless bikesharing services in 2021, which reduced the carsharing and bikesharing use in some parts of the city. The analysis was conducted using GIS software to assess the indicators. The findings of the study are useful to identify the areas that should be improved in terms of walkability and pedestrian accessibility in order to increase the use of shared mobility services in Palermo.

References

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[2] Schlossberg M., Brown N., "Comparing Transit-Oriented Development Sites by Walkability Indicators", *Transportation Research Record*, 1887, 34-42 (2004).